

USE OF SYNONYMS IN SHAROF RASHIDOV'S NOVEL "MIGHTY WAVE"

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Abstract: Lexical units exist in the language and form different paradigms based on different semantic relations. Synonymous, antonymic, graduonymic, paronymic, hyponymic relation to mother is such a linguistic relation. Synonymy. Lexemes that have different forms, but express the same concept in different colors and shades, are called synonyms. The relationship between synonymous lexemes is called synonymy or synonymous relationship. This article analyzes the use of synonyms in Sharaf Rashidov's work "The Mighty Wave" and their stylistic features.

Keywords: Synonymy, lexeme, speech units, word combinations, independent lexeme, lexical words, word combinations, "Powerful wave".

УПОТРЕБЛЕНИЕ СИНОНИМОВ В РОМАНЕ ШАРОФА РАШИДОВА «МОГУЧАЯ ВОЛНА»

Аннотация: Лексические единицы существуют в языке и образуют разные парадигмы, основанные на разных смысловых отношениях. Таким языковым отношением является синонимическое, антонимическое, градуонимическое, партонимическое, гипонимическое отношение к матери. Синонимия. Лексемы, имеющие разную форму, но выражающие одно и то же понятие в разных цветах и оттенках, называются синонимами. Отношения между синонимичными лексемами называются синонимией или синонимическими отношениями. В данной статье анализируется употребление синонимов в произведении Шарафа Рашидова «Могучая волна» и их стилистические особенности.

Ключевые слова: Синонимия, лексема, речевые единицы, словосочетания, самостоятельная лексема, лексические слова, словосочетания, «Мощная волна».

INTRODUCTION

Synonymous words (synonyms) are words that express a common concept (meaning) with different pronunciation and spelling. Synonyms differ from each other in terms of additional meaning, emotional color, and application. Big, great, big, great, big, big, gigantic, huge, big, huge, big, big, big, big, big, big, big, big, big, giant The words "great", "great", "great" and "huge" are used for things that are very large in size, and the words "giant" and "magnificent" are used for things that are very large in size. Large is rarely used. Gigant is characteristic of the book style and is mainly used in relation to place and construction.

MAIN PART

The phenomenon of language units having the same meaning is called synonymy. This phenomenon is divided into lexical (lexical) synonymy, phraseological synonymy, and syntactic synonymy, depending on the linguistic units. A group of words that are synonymous with each other is called a line of synonyms. A line of synonyms consists of two or more words. The line of synonyms is composed of many words. Ambiguous words can have one or more synonyms with a specific meaning or meanings. For example: the word "finish" with one meaning belongs to the group of words to finish, to complete, to finish, and with another meaning to "do away", to lose, to destroy.

The expression scheme of lexemes in the meaning line is different. Some of them are:

- 1) positive or negative assessment or attitude;
- 2) lexeme is a term indicating the period of use of the form: "old", "new", "very new", "archaic", "historical";
- 3) lexeme is a term that indicates the scope of application of the form: "characteristic", "speech-specific", "bookish", "elevation" are united around this lexeme and form a circle of meaning. Dominant lexemization, all the expressions listed above are neutral, neutral. For example, on the basis of the expressions "bookishness", "highness" a synonymous line [katta]-[ulkan]-[bahayabat] is created.

Based on the needs of the times, society gets rid of unnecessary consumption and continues to enrich itself with new ones. Lines of meaning in speech are filled and expanded with speech units, word combinations, independent lexeme types, lexical words, word combinations, speech transitions. These, as contextual synonyms, are a means of providing the beauty and richness of speech.

Spring blooms and gives life to the world even in the difficult days of the bloody war, which brought so much grief and sorrow to everyone. (page 7)

Sadness, grief - a feeling of mental suffering that appears in a person, such a state of mind. The word anxiety is used more colloquially. The word grief is paired with the word worry and gives the expression "spiritual distress." In the speech, the word grief is also used in this sense. The word kulfat strongly expresses this meaning. The words "pain" and "pain" have a strong emphasis on mental suffering. These words are used in pairs to express the content more strongly. Anduh is an old, bookish word with a poetic color. It is often used as a double word with the word grief, where it expresses the meaning more strongly. In the novel "The Mighty Wave", we will consider the skill of the creator Sharaf Rashidov in using meaningful words through the following examples:

The children saw the plight of Polat, who had sparks of hatred in his eyes, and were afraid and confused. (page 12)

To be afraid, to be confused is used in the sense of feeling fear, being frightened, stuttering. The expression "to be confused" has an artistic coloring compared to the word "to be afraid".

Polat took Bahor under his protection, but he did not realize that he himself had become the one who listened to every word of the girl and obeyed her. (page 13)

To listen, to obey - to follow someone's order, assignment, guidance, to do what he said. Obedience is mostly characteristic of bookish speech.

...every time he came in, he would exaggerate and exaggerate about what was going on in the world, Khalil would listen carefully to the beautiful and sweet words of his neighbor, which were typed like beads. (page 20)

It is used in the meaning of adding, exaggerating, exaggerating, multiplying.

After all, isn't the friendship between a playful girl and a cheerful boy different from the friendship between a mature girl and a teenage boy? (p. 20)

CONCLUSION

Playful, cheerful, physically and mentally full of energy, active, playful, fast-moving, physically active, fun-loving, humor-loving; cheerful, cheerful. Among synonyms, "horny" is often used as a dominant word. Stylistically, it is characteristic of artistic, scientific, journalistic and conversational styles.

We can see that Sharaf Rashidov used synonyms effectively in his novel "The Mighty Wave". Synonyms in the artistic text served as an important factor in creating a style in the artistic work, avoiding repetition, clearly describing the event, strengthening the situation, and performing artistic and stylistic tasks.

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